

Advertising as a Linguistic and Cultural Phenomenon

Jurayeva Maksuda Mukhammadovna

*Associate professor, PhD, French Philology Department, Bukhara State University
m.m.jurayeva@buxdu.uz*

Arashova Rukhshona

3rd year student of Bukhara State University, Faculty of Foreign Languages

Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of advertising language as a cultural phenomenon and analyzes advertising texts in Uzbek and French. Advertising is important not only as a means of presenting products or services, but also as a means of reflecting social and cultural values. The article studies the linguistic features, styles and cultural contexts of advertising texts in Uzbek and French. It also analyzes the specificity of advertising language, its role in communicating with the audience, and how culture affects the content of advertising. It examines how the specific aspects and traditions of Uzbek and French cultures are expressed in advertising language, as well as the importance of language and its communicative functions in this process. The results of this study contribute to a deeper understanding of the relationship between advertising language and culture and provide an opportunity to look at advertising practices from a new perspective.

Keywords: Advertising, language, culture, communication, linguistics, symbolism, connotation, cultural values, creativity, globalization, social impact, advertising texts, audience, cultural traditions, advertising strategies, interaction between language and culture, visual communication, advertising media, cultural studies.

INTRODUCTION

Advertising is an integral part of modern social life, which plays an important role not only in promoting products and services, but also in reflecting the interaction of culture and language. The unique values, traditions and language features of each nation are clearly reflected in advertising texts. The Uzbek and French languages, along with their cultures, offer different styles and language features in the field of advertising. In this article, we will study the complex relationship between language and culture through the analysis of advertising texts in the Uzbek and French languages.

The uniqueness of the advertising language, its communicative functions and role in communicating with the audience, as well as the influence of culture on the content of advertising are considered. We will consider how the unique aspects, traditions and language systems of the Uzbek and French cultures are expressed in advertising texts, the importance of language in this process and its communicative functions. The results of this study contribute to a deeper understanding of the relationship between advertising language and culture and provide an opportunity to look at advertising practices from a new perspective. In the course of the article, we will examine how advertising language is formed and developed as a cultural phenomenon, and also shed light on the interaction between language and culture in this process.

METHODS AND ANALYSIS

Advertising texts written in Uzbek and French were collected, advertising texts were divided into different categories, the grammatical, lexical and stylistic features of each language were studied, diction and phraseological units used in advertising texts in Uzbek and French were analyzed, metaphors, analogies and other stylistic techniques were identified in advertising texts, social and economic factors influencing the content of advertising were identified, the characteristics of the target audience for both languages were studied, and the suitability of advertising texts for these audiences was analyzed.

DISCUSSION

Advertising (from the Latin word “reclamare” – “to shout, call”) is an activity carried out with the aim of presenting a product, service or idea to the public and encouraging them to buy it. In modern society, advertising is recognized not only as a marketing tool, but also as a cultural phenomenon.

The role of advertising in society is determined by the following functions:

- Informing (providing information about the product/service)
- Persuading (encouraging the consumer to buy)
- Reminding (keeping the product/service in memory)
- Cultural (reflecting and forming the values of society)
- Social (strengthening social norms)

The stages of development of advertising in Uzbek and French societies have their own characteristics. While advertising in France has a long history, appearing in the form of newspaper advertisements in the 18th century, in Uzbekistan, modern advertising has a relatively recent history, especially after independence. [1]

Advertising language is a separate linguistic phenomenon, which is characterized by such features as brevity, expressiveness, and emotionality. Advertising texts have the following linguistic features:

a) Lexical features:

- Use of advertising vocabulary
- Activity of emotional-expressive lexicon
- Use of neologisms, occasionalisms, and borrowed words
- Use of figurative words such as metaphor, metonymy, and simile

b) Syntactic features:

- Abundance of elliptical (incomplete) sentences
- Use of rhetorical questions and exclamations
- Activity of imperative sentences
- Use of parallel constructions and repetitions

c) Phonetic features:

- Alliteration and assonance
- Rhythm and rhyme
- Intonation features
- Graphic features:
 - Use of different fonts and colors

- Specific use of punctuation marks
- Graphic accentuation methods. [2]

The linguistic features of Uzbek advertisements are closely related to the national language and culture. The following linguistic features are widely found in Uzbek advertisements:

Lexical features:

Use of national-cultural words and expressions: words such as “*dasturxon*”, “*mehmon*”, “*to’y*”, “*bayram*”.

Use of emotional-expressive vocabulary in the Uzbek language: “*shirin*”, “*laziz*”, “*so’z*”, “*ajoyib*”.

Voice reflecting national values: “*hurmat*”, “*ehtirom*”, “*oila*”, “*farzand*”.

Example: “Rafaello - a sign of attention and respect for your dear people” (Rafaello chocolate advertisement).

Syntactic features:

Frequent use of imperative mood: “*Oling!*”, “*Taste!*”, “*Benefit!*”

Use of rhetorical interrogative sentences: “*Are you looking for a quality product?*”

Use of parallel constructions:

Example: “Dice - the successor of our national traditions, Dice - the beauty of your table, Dice - the happiness of the family” (Dice oil advertisement).

Pragmatic features:

Use of forms of respect: Wide use of the pronoun “*You*”.

National features of forms of address: “*Dear customers*”, “*Dear compatriots*”.

As a result of a comparative analysis of Uzbek and French advertisements, the following similarities and differences were identified:

Similarities:

Wide use of emotional-expressive vocabulary in advertisements in both languages

Use of words and phrases reflecting national values

Use of effective syntactic constructions.

Differences:

While concepts such as collective values, family, and respect predominate in Uzbek advertisements, ideas of individuality, self-confidence, and enjoyment of life are more common in French advertisements.

Traditionality is more evident in Uzbek advertisements, while innovative approaches are more evident in French advertisements.

Whether puns and puns are used more in French advertisements, figurative expressions and metaphors predominate in Uzbek advertisements. [3]

Examples:

Uzbek: “*A holiday is sweeter with cola!*” (Coca-Cola advertisement).

French: “*Un verre ça va, trois verres bonjour les dégados!*” (One glass is enough, three glasses are the beginning of problems!) (Social advertising against alcohol).

RESULTS

Uzbek-language advertisements focus more on traditional values, family ties, and national traditions. For example, advertisements for family events or national holidays use national colors and symbols. French-language advertisements, on the other hand, are more individualistic, aesthetically pleasing, and modern. These advertisements often address topics related to modern lifestyles, fashion, and art. Uzbek advertisements often use simple, straightforward language, which helps them reach a wide audience. Competitive prices and quality are emphasized.

French advertisements, on the other hand, use more sophisticated lexical and stylistic devices. Metaphors, alliteration, and humor are widely used, which increases the aesthetic appeal of the advertisement. Uzbek advertisements often take into account family and collective values, and are therefore more likely to appeal to families or communities. French advertisements, on the other hand, are more targeted at a younger and more urbanized audience, which increases interest in innovative products and services.

Uzbek advertisements often try to attract consumers by highlighting viewing opportunities, discounts and promotions. French advertisements, on the other hand, focus more on emotional appeal, storytelling and highlighting the high quality of the brand. Uzbek advertisements may emphasize social issues, such as a healthy lifestyle and environmentally friendly products. French advertisements, on the other hand, often focus on gender equality, social justice and environmental issues. Uzbek advertisements tend to include more traditional elements, such as national colors and symbols. French advertisements may be based on more modern design and aesthetics, which increases their visual appeal. [4]

CONCLUSION

The study of the relationship between advertising language and cultural phenomena reveals the specific features of advertising texts in Uzbek and French. The approaches to advertising of both cultures differ in terms of language and aesthetic aspects, target audiences, which reflect their social values and traditions. In general, advertising language is not only a means of selling products or services, but also plays an important role in the formation of cultural identity and the expression of social values. By analyzing advertising texts in Uzbek and French, we can see cross-cultural differences and similarities, which helps to develop new strategies and approaches in the field of advertising. Thus, the study of advertising language leads to a deeper understanding of culture and serves to improve communication processes on a global scale.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdullaeva M. Reklama matnlarining lingvopragmatik xususiyatlari. – Toshkent: Fan, 2018. – 154 b.
2. Boltaboeva H. O'zbek reklamalarining lingvomadaniy xususiyatlari. – Toshkent: Turon zamin ziyo, 2020. – 180 b.
3. Karimov S. Zamonaviy o'zbek reklamalari: lingvistik tahlil. – Toshkent: Tafakkur, 2019. – 124 b.
4. Adam J.M., Bonhomme M. L'argumentation publicitaire. – Paris: Nathan, 2017. – 238 p.
5. Barthes R. Mythologies. – Paris: Seuil, 1970. – 267 p.
6. Charaudeau P. Le discours publicitaire, genre discursif. – Paris: Mots, 2018. – 195 p.
7. Cook G. The Discourse of Advertising. – London: Routledge, 2001. 256 p.
8. Goddard A. The Language of Advertising. – London: Routledge, 2018. – 198 p.
9. Guidère M. Publicité et traduction. – Paris: L'Harmattan, 2019. – 325 p.
10. Hall E.T. Beyond Culture. – New York: Anchor Books, 1989. – 320 p.

11. Mukhammadovna, Jurayeva Maksuda. "Media relations in french discourse." MIDDLE EUROPEAN SCIENTIFIC BULLETIN ISSN (2021): 2694-9970.
12. Maqsuda, Jurayeva. "Yozma matbuot diskursining funktsional xususiyatlari." Ilm sarchashmalari 6 (2021).
13. М Жўраева Pour une analyse fonctionnelle et discursive des titres de la presse française Educational Research in Universal Sciences 1 (7), 422-428
14. Maqsuda, J., & Madina, T. (2023). THE TITLE-THE FIRST WORD THAT THE AUTHOR SAYS TO HIS READER. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12, 146-147.
15. Maqsuda, J., & Ferouza, F. (2023). Modern Mass Media: Characteristics, Functions and Types. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(6), 4-7.
16. JM Muhammadovna Matbuot va jurnalistika ФАН ВА ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР ТАРАККИЎТИ ИЛМИЙ - ТЕХНИКАВИЙ ЖУРНАЛ 4 (7), 235-238.
17. Исломов, Д. Ш. "Поэтические формы как культуроведческий компонент при обучении иностранному языку." *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал* 1 (2015): 23-29.
18. Ванцова, Н. В., Д. Исламов, and Т. М. Хусяинов. "Возможности использования проектной методики при преподавании иностранных языков." *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал* 10 (2016): 31-34.
19. Shomurodovich, Islomov Dilshod. "THE EMERGENCE OF PSYCHOLINGUISTICS, THE SCIENTISTS'SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL VIEWS AND ITS CONNECTION WITH OTHER SCIENCES." *JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY BULLETIN* 6.5 (2023): 213-218.
20. Islomov, D. "THE ROLE OF PHONOSTYLISTIC UNITS AND PHONEMES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING FRENCH TO ADULTS IN THE ANALYSIS OF EXAMPLES." *Конференции*. 2021.
21. Islomov, D. Sh. "THE DIFFERENTIATION ASPECTS OF UZBEK AND FRENCH PHONETICS." *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research* 10.11 (2023): 47-51.
22. Shomurodovich, I. D. L. E. "ROLE DE L'EMOTION EN PHONOPSYCHOLOGIE." (2023): 77-79.